

Migrating for the good? A comparative assessment of educational achievements of Bolivian-origin youths in Argentina, Bolivians in Bolivia, and Argentine natives

Carolina V. Zuccotti

Abstract

Studies on migrant integration has long dominated the agenda of sociologists and economists around the world. But as one becomes acquainted with such literature, it is easy to see that is dominated by two types of approaches. First, there is a predominance of studies comparing how migrants and their children compare to natives in destination countries. Second, most research on migrant integration is centred on South-North moves. Using large-scale census microdata (2001-2012), this study addresses both concerns by studying educational outcomes and patterns of educational reproduction among the children of Bolivian migrants in Argentina, and how these compare to those of native Argentine children and those of non-migrants at origin. Findings show that while, on average, Bolivian-origin children in Argentina get higher educational outcomes than Argentine natives, the opposite is observed when compared to non-migrants in Bolivia. These results are further examined in relation to parental education and year.

1 Introduction

Studies on migrant integration and, in particular, on the socioeconomic incorporation of migrants and their children in destination societies, has long dominated the agenda of sociologists and economists around the world. But as one becomes acquainted with such literature, it is easy to see that it is dominated by two types of studies or approaches—which I seek to challenge in this article. First, there is a predominance of studies comparing how migrants and their children compare to natives in destination countries. While extremely relevant to understand processes of integration (and exclusion), studying how migrants and their children compare to natives in destination provides only a partial view of the outcomes of migration. Migrants, especially economic migrants, move to make their lives and those of the one surrounding them (family, children) better (Feliciano, 2005; Sjaastad, 1962). This means that, when possible, those who decide to make a move to another country will often seek to achieve two aims. First, they will seek to improve not only their own lives, but especially the lives of their children relative to their own; and second, migrants will seek to provide their children with a better life compared to what this would have been back home. While the perspective that considers parental origins and/or educational and social mobility processes has gained a relevant place in migration studies (Li & Heath, 2016; Portes & Fernandez-Kelly, 2008), the number of studies that consider the country of origin vs. country of destination perspective (Beauchemin, 2014; Guveli et al., 2017, Author XX) is much more limited.

Second, most research on migrant integration is centred on South-North moves, even though that constitutes only a fraction of international migration at the global level. South-South migration or migration within the Global South—broadly understood as migration that occurs between less developed countries in Asia, Africa and Latin America (Bakewell, 2009; Campillo-Carrete, 2013)—is gaining importance both in statistical terms and in research and policy debates. According to data from 2017, around 38% of individuals living in a foreign country were South-South migrants, while South-North migrants were 35%.¹ However, research on integration patterns of Southern migrants and their children residing in the Global South is limited, and even more limited is the evidence showing differences and similarities between migrants and non-migrants at origin.

¹ United Nations; Department of Economic and Social Affairs; Population Division (2017a)

Using large-scale census microdata (Minnesota Population Center, 2020), this article addresses both concerns through the study of one key outcome of integration—the education of the children of migrants—in key migration corridor in the Global South—that between Bolivia (as an origin country) and Argentina (as a destination). Specifically, I study educational outcomes and patterns of educational reproduction among the children of Bolivian migrants in Argentina, and how these compare to those of native Argentine children and those of non-migrants at origin. The article answers the following questions: How do educational outcomes of migrant-origin, native, and non-migrant groups compare, and how are they affected by their parents' education? Do patterns of educational reproduction vary across groups? Given this (potential variation), do we also observe variation in educational outcomes (and therefore variation in educational gaps) across diverse parental educational levels? The fundamental theoretical assumptions that guide this research are, first, that the educational level of parents (regardless of their migrant background) plays a fundamental role in the educational opportunities of their children (Blau & Duncan, 1967); and second, that educational achievements, as well as the processes of educational reproduction/mobility, may vary according to migrant origins (Chiswick & DebBurman, 2004; Crul, Schneider, Keskiner, & Lelie, 2017; Feliciano & Lanuza, 2017; Kao & Thompson, 2003, Author XX) and to country contexts (Breen & Müller, 2020; Neidhöfer, Ciaschi, & Gasparini, 2021).

Argentina is an interesting case study to explore migrant integration processes. The country has been and continues to be a key receiving destination, and the migratory phenomenon has constituted a central component of its population growth (Bengochea & Pellegrino, 2023) and history (Oszlak, 1997). The greatest number of immigrants up until the mid-1950s were from the Global North (mainly Spain and Italy), and they constituted around 30% of the total population in 1914 (Cerrutti, 2009). Over time, this predominance of European origins slowly shifted in favour of South American origins, which characterize most of arrivals in Argentina in the last 30 years. Data from the 2010 Census show, for example, that almost 80% of immigrants in Argentina were from neighbouring countries and Peru. The growing immigration of South Americans has been related to Argentina's particularly attractive position in the regional context, especially in terms of economic opportunities, development, and favourable migration laws and rights (Cerrutti & Parrado, 2015). According to 2015 data (which does not include the most recent Venezuelan immigrations), the majority of South American immigrants residing in Argentina come from Paraguay (32%) and Bolivia (20%); there are also considerable numbers of Peruvian (9%), Chilean (10%) and Uruguayan (6%) origins (United Nations; Department of Economic and Social Affairs; Population Division, 2017b). Immigration from Bolivia constitutes, therefore, one of the most important immigration waves.

Though—as also observed for other South American groups—the number of Bolivians has greatly increased in the 1990s and 2000s, immigration from Bolivia is, nevertheless, not a recent phenomenon. The earliest arrivals can be dated back to the XIX century and predominated in the neighbouring provinces of Jujuy and Salta, up until the mid-XX Century. This immigration was strongly associated with agricultural labour (Sassone & Cortes, 2014). Over time, emigration became a more massive phenomenon, and this also implied a dispersion in the Argentinean territory, directly mostly towards urban areas, Buenos Aires in particular. The long-term presence of Bolivians implies that there is an important number of descendants, who are at school or have left school recently. Bolivian migrants have, on average, lower educational levels and perform less skilled occupations compared to other groups and the majority Argentine population (Cerrutti, 2009). They also have high poverty rates (Lieutier, 2019) and tend to live in spatially segregated and deprived neighbourhoods (Mera & Marcos, 2015, Author XX). The children of Bolivian migrants in Argentina—in whom I focus in this study—are, therefore, exposed to a series of family and context disadvantages, which may, in turn, affect their educational outcomes.

2 Educational reproduction, migration and country contexts

To reflect on the various explanatory mechanisms associated with migration and education, a good starting point is to think of how education and educational reproduction is studied for the majoritarian population (which, in this case, includes two main groups: Argentines and Bolivians). And then hypothesize how this may work for a member of a migrant community—who moves between two societies which may (or may not) have diverse educational reproduction patterns.

One of the key determinants of individuals' educational attainment—perhaps the most important one—is the educational attainment of their parent(s). The literature on educational reproduction and educational mobility has shown substantive evidence of this empirical regularity. However, not all individuals are subject to the same effects. Following the aims of this study there are two key dimensions by which the relationship between parental education and that of their offspring may vary: the country context, and the migration status. In the next paragraphs I first delineate a general theory of educational reproduction; then I move on to explore how this varies for Argentina and Bolivia; I end this section with a discussion of how and why educational reproduction may vary across migrant and non-migrant groups, and what the implication for a migrant and their children may be to migrate to countries with different levels of educational reproduction.

2.1 *The general model*

Goldthorpe's "mobility strategies" (Goldthorpe, 2000) are a useful starting point to reflect on parent-child relationships and why, or why not, they may vary across the various groups. According to this approach, one of the key explanations behind the social rigidity of societies—present not only in Western societies but also in Latin America—is that the main objective of families is to reproduce the social class of origin, that is, to avoid downward mobility. But not all families have the same types of strategies, and Goldthorpe differentiates between strategies from above (high-class) and strategies from below (low class).

Among low-class families with low-educated parents, reproduction occurs because higher education is usually not presented as the most desired option, since it implies a greater risk (for example, in case of failure) and more resources (especially for access to university). In particular, the reward (mediated by entry into the labour market) is delayed, and it may be something that families cannot afford. Alternatives such as vocational training, early entry into the labour market and short mobility (e.g., towards lower technical occupations) may seem more desirable. By contrast, among the medium-high socioeconomic sectors with highly educated parents, education is the main way to maintain their social class. Therefore, the encouragement and motivation to continue studying are more present, and parents are better able to help their children, for example, in solving homework. In addition to the positive effect of parental education, high-class families have additional socioeconomic resources to make social reproduction happen. For example, a higher income can favour moving to a better neighbourhood with better quality schools, or paying for individual tutorship, or sending their children to private schools. This is known as compensatory class effects (Bernardi, 2014).

2.2 *Educational reproduction in Latin America: Argentina and Bolivia compared*

Thinking about these processes in Latin America, evidence shows that educational levels in the region have improved greatly in the last century, and more people now access primary, secondary and, more recently, university education (UNDP, 2021). This has implied an increase in absolute rates of intergenerational educational mobility (Cruces, Domench, & Gasparini, 2012; Jiménez & Jiménez, 2019; Muñoz, 2022), driven especially by an increasing likelihood of individuals with low-educated parents to complete secondary schooling (Neidhöfer et al., 2021). While this has implied a closing gap in education, at the same time, Torche (2021) notes that educational mobility is, to a great extent, explained by educational expansion policies in Latin

America, which facilitated the massive entrance of children in the educational system. This means that while opportunities for access to education have improved, they continue to be strongly determined by the socioeconomic conditions of families of origin, including parental educational levels. In particular, there is an agreement on a strong degree of reproduction at the top of the distribution, that is, among those who have highly educated parents (Dalle, Jorrat, & Riveiro, 2018; Neidhöfer et al., 2021; Torche, 2021). Latin America continues to be one of the most unequal regions in the world (UNDP, 2021) and the patterns of educational reproduction help maintain this position.

Both Argentina and Bolivia have been part of these processes of increasing rates of educational mobility and educational expansion. Figure 1, based on census microdata from the last two censuses—to be used later on in the analysis (Minnesota Population Center, 2020)—shows that educational attainments have improved across cohorts in both countries. This is particularly striking in Bolivia, where the share of individuals with less than primary education starts very high for the cohorts up to the 1940s and reduces dramatically over time. This applies both to men and women, though in Bolivia women have tended to be less educated than men, especially up to the 1970 cohort. For the 1980 cohort, educational distributions are much more similar between countries. More recently, there are some indications that suggest that while in Argentina the process of educational expansion stabilizes, it continues in Bolivia. Figure 2—based on the same data—shows the probability of having finished secondary education for individuals between 19 and 25 years old for the last two census waves (2001 and 2010/2012). I distinguish between all individuals and those residing with their parent(s), who will be the object of study later on. There are three clear trends. First, while patterns of educational attainment do not change much in Argentina between both census waves, in Bolivia there is a clear improvement in education, for both men and women.² Second, those who reside with at least one parent have, on average, higher education compared to the entire age distribution. This pattern, which happens in both countries and genders, but with greater strength in Bolivia, probably reflects processes of self-selection: remaining in the parental home is likely a means towards attaining a better education. Third, while in Argentina, women surpass men in educational achievements, in Bolivia this only occurs among those who co-reside with parents.

² Note that for Bolivia, the 19-age group stands as an outlier: on average, more than 65% have finished secondary education, while this reduces to around 50-55 for individuals with 20 to 25.

Figure 1: Education across cohorts (25-64 yrs), by country and gender

Source: Own calculations based on IPUMS (2001, 2010 & 2012)

Figure 2: Probability of secondary+ (19-25 yrs)

Source: Own calculations based on IPUMS (2001, 2010 & 2012)

Figure 3: Probability of secondary+ (19-25), by parental years of education

Source: Own calculations based on IPUMS (2001, 2010 & 2012)

Next to this, Figure 3 shows, only for those who co-reside with parents, how educational attainment varies according to parental years of education. While for both countries and waves there is a positive association between parental and children education, some differences emerge. First, the educational gap between Argentines and Bolivians—which favours the latter across all parental years of education for men, and up to 12-13 parental years of education for women—is larger among those who have low educated parents. This is observed for both genders, though male gaps are larger. These effects become more evident in the second wave, where the greater upward educational mobility from the bottom in Bolivia is evident for both genders. In other words, the shape of the relationship becomes flatter for this country in 2012, indicating a lower dependence on parental education. Second, in both countries and for both genders, those in the most recent wave seem to be less able to transfer parental educational resources: in particular, those who have parents with 12 years of education or more (i.e., parents with secondary or lower secondary education at least) have lower chances of finishing high school in the second wave (compared to those in the first wave).³ In Argentina, however, this is not accompanied—as in a Bolivia—by an increase in the chances of the lower educated sectors. Some of these processes of educational mobility have also been documented in cross-national studies of the region. For example, using data from IPUMS, Muñoz (2022) studies the probability of having completed primary education for 14-18 and 14-25 year old individuals whose (co-resident) older generations have incomplete primary. He shows that absolute educational mobility is higher in Argentina than in Bolivia for the 1970s and 1980s cohort, but lower for the 1990s cohort. Similarly, Neidhöfer et al. (2021), who study individuals over 20 years old from 1940 to 1990 cohorts, show that Bolivia has made greater improvements in terms of educational mobility over time—measured as the probability of attaining secondary education among those with parents with less than secondary. This effect is particularly strong for the 1990 cohort, for whom the probabilities are almost 10% higher in Bolivia than in Argentina. The authors also show greater reproduction at the top among the Bolivian population, compared to Argentina, something that we also observe in our data and for both years, but mainly for men, while for women this applies (with a smaller advantage) to those with secondary educated parents (i.e., 12-13 years of education).

These patterns serve as a context to explore what may happen to a child of a Bolivian migrant residing in Argentina. In the next paragraphs I first discuss what difference may it make to have migrant origins; then I examine how this may interact with the receiving context.

2.3 *Migration and educational reproduction: migrant-origin & context effects*

The previous section showed us, first, that parental education is one of the most important predictors of individuals' education; and second, that this relationship may vary not only across contexts but also over time. Below I relate these statements with the migration literature. I discuss how having migrant origins and moving across contexts with different patterns of educational reproduction may play a role in the understanding of variation in educational outcomes. In so doing, this discussion will also shed light on our interpretation of the 'benefits' and 'drawbacks' of migration.

2.3.1 *What difference does it make to have migrant origins?*

While Goldthorpe's argument on the mechanisms of educational reproduction may sound plausible for the majority, one might think that this may not necessarily apply to those families who seek, through migration, to improve the quality of life of themselves and their children (especially in relation to that it had been back home) (Sjaastad, 1962). This means that, especially among those with lower educational levels and lower socioeconomic resources, migration might

³ Note that Neidhöfer et al. (2021) only find a decrease in the top reproduction for the adult population in Argentina, while the situation for Bolivia is that of stability or slight increase (recall that I work with a very specific sample). If anything, this would reinforce the positive advantage of Bolivians in Bolivia.

be a way towards educational mobility. This may lead us to see a lower dependence of migrant-origin children on their parental educational backgrounds, which may in turn lead to observe better educational achievements for migrant-origin groups, not only compared to those in the destination country but also compared to those left behind. Among the possible explanations that promote this, the literature has highlighted both the higher levels of motivation and/or aspirations of children and adults of migrant origin (Cebolla-Boado, González Ferrer, & Nuhoğlu Soysal, 2021; Feliciano, 2020; Kao & Tienda, 1998; Polavieja, Fernández-Reino, & Ramos, 2018) and the role of ethnic capital (Borjas, 1995; Lee & Zhou, 2014). A large number of qualitative studies in Argentina reveal that this is the case of several migrant groups, including Bolivians: education is conceived as a channel for social mobility and as a resource to improve the families' socioeconomic conditions (Gavazzo, Beheran, & Novaro, 2014; Gavazzo & Espul, 2020; Lemmi, Morzilli, & Moretto, 2018), and migrant-origin families develop strategies to make this happen, e.g., such as sending their children to better and more distant schools.

As we think of better-educated migrants and natives, things might be different, due to their often unequal distribution of "class compensatory effects" (Bernardi, 2014). Continuing with Goldthorpe's arguments, to reproduce their class position, middle and upper-middle classes not only motivate their children to continue studying, but also have a series of compensatory class resources that facilitate this process—such as a good job or high incomes that allow access to tutoring, social networks, knowledge of the school system, access to better schools, etc. Although more highly educated migrants may have comparable educational resources to those of natives and non-migrants, they are likely to have less socio-economic compensatory resources, especially if we think about the generally more precarious processes of socio-economic and spatial insertion of the first generations (Carrasco & Suárez, 2019; Cerrutti, 2009; Heath & Cheung, 2007). While motivation may well be present among migrants who want to recover, through their children, their class position at origin, and may translate in greater effort compared to their native counterparts at both origin and destination, this might not be enough to compensate for their lower compensatory resources. This may lead to see a disadvantage among migrant-origin groups with middle-highly educated parents.

In sum, if mobility strategies are susceptible to variation according to migrant origin, this may have implications for how inequality in educational achievement looks like for individuals of migrant and non-migrant origins (be these from origin or destination countries). In other words, due to the expected variation across groups in terms of the relationship between parents' and children's education, I also expect to see variation in educational gaps across groups and across educational origins.

2.3.2 What difference does it make to move across contexts with different regimes of educational reproduction?

Moving across countries with different levels of educational reproduction means that individuals are exposed to contexts in which the value of educational origins may vary. The case under study is particularly interesting in this respect, since Bolivia experienced significant progress in upward educational mobility from the bottom, a process that we see more clearly in the 2012 Census wave, at least for those who co-reside with their parents. Furthermore, for the same sample of co-residents, reproduction at the top appears higher in Bolivia, especially for men. This means, on the one hand, that young individuals with low educated parents in Bolivia tend to gain more from their disadvantaged origins; and, on the other, that young individuals with middle-high (or middle, in the case of women) educated parents in Bolivia tend to be better able to express that advantage into their own education. What may be the implications of this when studying the children of migrants in comparative perspective?

First, one may hypothesize that migrant-origin individuals in Argentina will not be exposed to the observed patterns of increased educational expansion in Bolivia. This seems particularly relevant if we consider that most emigrants (i.e., the parental generation) have, in general, low

educational levels. Of course, this apparent disadvantage of having left an “educationally mobile country” might be compensated, among other factors, by the above-mentioned motivational assets or by the specific residence of migrants in destination, many of them located in the city of Buenos Aires, where educational achievements tend to be higher (I try to control for this with a departmental-level measure of education). Second, one may also hypothesize that if intergenerational reproduction of those with middle-high educational levels appears to be stronger in Bolivia than in Argentina (especially for men, and to a lesser extent for women), this means that the children of those who left might, again, not benefit from such processes happening at origin.⁴ In addition, the potential lack of compensatory factors in destination may make these differences even more prominent. Having said these, the extent to which migrant-origin individuals may somehow adapt to the patterns observed in an Argentina is, of course, an open question. Factors such as discrimination and stigmatization (Behtoui & Neergaard, 2009; Dawkins, 2004; Di Stasio & Heath, 2019; Hanson & Hawley, 2011) may also play a role in educational success, especially for a relatively visible group, such as the population of Bolivian origin (Beech & Princz, 2012; Domenech 2014; Novaro, 2012). What we know for sure is that migrant-origin individuals will not be exposed anymore to the institutional context of Bolivia, which is likely responsible, at least, for the process of educational expansion (Torche, 2021). Finally, although with the present data it is not possible to unpack the “black box” behind the potential gaps between the groups, the analysis will provide with a starting point to discuss new ways to measure and evaluate the outcomes of migration.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data and sample

The analysis is based on census microdata for Argentina (2001, 2010) and Bolivia (2001, 2012). Data comes from the Integrated Public Use Microdata Series (IPUMS) international (Minnesota Population Center, 2020). While relatively old, census microdata has a series of key advantages, including the large number of cases and, hence, the possibility of working with each migrant group separately, and the possibility of combining individual and household information into one analysis. The unit of analysis are young individuals between 14 and 25 years old residing with at least one parent (identified as the household head and his/her partner). The census does not contain, as standard stratification surveys, retrospective parental information; I hence need to reconstruct it within each household. The analysis compares three groups: Bolivians in Bolivia (native Bolivians of two Bolivian parents; one parent, if there is no partner in the household), second-generation Bolivians in Argentina (individuals born in Argentina of two Bolivians parents; one parent, if there is no partner in the household); and Argentineans in Argentina (native Argentines of two Argentine parents; one parent, if there is no partner in the household). The total sample includes around two-hundred and thirty thousand Bolivians in Bolivia, around one million native Argentines, and around eight-thousand Bolivian-origin individuals in Argentina. Note that, given the age range analysed, this study refers to children whose parents are relatively long-term residents, probably arrived before the 1990s and with 14 years of residence or more (even though I cannot precisely confirm this with this data).⁵

Given that I work with individuals co-habiting with their parents, it is likely that there is some sort of selection, especially among the oldest groups. I showed that individuals who live with their parents tend to be more educated. This effect was particularly strong in Bolivia. Another difference between the countries is that, for the studied age group, individuals in Bolivia are less likely to be

⁴ Note that in both countries reproduction at the top reduces between both years—at least for those co-residing with parents—, but the positive gap in favour of Bolivia remains the same.

⁵ Data from the official 2010 census shows that around 38% of Bolivians have arrived before 1991; 25% between 1991 and 2001, and around 37% between 2002 and 2010.

a son or a daughter of the household head; conversely, they are more likely to be household heads or their partners (figures available upon request). These effects might point to a stronger self-selection of Bolivians co-habiting with their parents, which means that the effects we find need to be considered under this assumption.

3.2 Variables

The analysis focuses on two measures of educational attainment: the probability of having finished primary education for 14- to 18-year-old children; and the probability of having completed secondary education for 19- to 25-year-old youngsters. The main explanatory variable is the parental educational level, which I measure in years (from 0 to 17, where 12-13 years express roughly completion of secondary education). I have considered the maximum between parents, when available. Other variables considered in the multivariate analysis are: at the individual level, sex and age; at the parental level, their activity (single workless, single working, couple workless-workless, couple working-workless and couple workless workless); at the household and housing levels, ownership (owner or not), level of overcrowding (number of household members per room), piped water (yes, no) and sewage disposal (yes, no). Moreover, I considered a variable at the departmental level: the share of 20 to 45-year-old individuals with secondary education or more, to have a certain control of educational opportunities in the area of residence. Although these variables are poor indicators of additional socioeconomic resources of the families (parental occupation would have been a good indicator for this), they are the only ones available in IPUMS.

4 Analysis

Following the precedent discussion, the analysis has a series of steps. First (section 4.1), I show descriptive statistics of the key variables under study for each comparison group, as well as the distribution of parental education. Next, I perform a series of multivariate models including the various controls. I use logistic regression and derive marginal effects, which I plot in graphs. All models are run separately for men and women. I start with a simple model (section 4.2) that includes an interaction between comparison group and wave (2001 and 2010/12), to have a general idea of average differences between groups over time. Next (section 4.3), I evaluate whether the relationship between parents and children varies also across groups and wave, through a triple interaction. Here I also pay particular attention to how this relationship changes as I include other control variables, to explore the hypothesis around compensatory effects. The results including all coefficients—based on the model with triple interactions—are shown in Table A2 in the Online Appendix.

4.1 Descriptives

Figure 4 shows the distribution of key dependent and independent variables. We observe, first, that finishing primary education is much more universalized than finishing secondary education, both in Argentina and in Bolivia. Second, differences between groups are much smaller for primary than for secondary completion; for the latter variable, Bolivian-origin individuals in Argentina have the lowest chances. This might be in part explained by their lower parental education, which denotes a negative selection of the migrant generation (i.e., they are less educated than those who remained). Third, while both Bolivians in Bolivia and Bolivians in Argentina seem to improve their attainment of secondary education between both waves, we do not observe this for native Argentines: again, this might be related to changes in the parental educational composition. Nevertheless, it is surprising that Bolivians in Bolivia do similar or even better than native Argentines: Bolivians have not only worse educated parents, on average, but also poorer household conditions (see Table A1 in the Online Appendix). Finally, women of all groups seem to be doing better than men. In order to unpack the content of these group differences, the next sections develop multivariate models, where I more closely look at differences by wave and parental education.

4.2 Multivariate models: exploration by waves

Figure 5 shows group effects on educational outcomes (Bolivians in Argentina and native Argentineans are compared with Bolivians in Bolivia, the zero line), separately for men and women, and for the two census waves (2001 and 2010/2012). The results are marginal effects obtained from four logistic regression models, each one plotted in the graphs: m1 controls for age; m2 adds parental education; m3 adds the remaining household-level variables (parental activity, ownership, level of overcrowding, piped water and sewage disposal); and m4 adds share of 20 to 45-year-old individuals with secondary education at the department level.

A first general outcome of this analysis is that results from m1, which resemble those observed in Figure 4, change greatly when we control for parental education (m2): Bolivian-origin individuals in Argentina (BolAR) gain an advantage with respect to native Argentines (ArgArg), and reduce the gap with respect to Bolivians in Bolivia (BolBol). Note that with the exception of women in 2001 when studying primary education, BolAR are doing equal or worse compared to BolBol. These changes in the coefficients emerge because Bolivian migrants (i.e., the parental generation) are the least educated group. Smaller changes, in the opposite direction, are further observed when introducing additional socioeconomic controls (m3 and m4), especially for secondary completion: BolAR have, on average, better housing conditions than BolBol, which leads the advantage of Bolivians in Bolivia to become even bigger. As for differences between waves, we see for primary education that the difference between BolAR and BolBol go from positive (women) or null (men) to negative, denoting a disadvantage for the most recent wave. However, the gap remains similar (and negative) for both genders when studying secondary completion. What remains clear from this analysis, is that Bolivian-origin individuals in Argentina tend to occupy an intermediate position: they do similar or worse than Bolivians Bolivia, and they do better than native Argentines. The next section provides a more detailed picture of these differences.

4.3 *Multivariate models: exploration by parental education and waves*

The inclusion of parental years of education as a conditioning variable yields interesting results. While, as expected, for all groups and waves the relationship between parents' and children's education is positive, the strength of this relationship varies.

First, a common trend for both educational outcomes, genders, and waves, is that the positive gap that BolAR have with respect to ArgArg happens among those who have low-educated parents only (generally up to 11-12 years, i.e., parents with lower secondary or secondary education). Second, in *primary education attainment*, BolAR women with low educated parents (up to 6-7 years) do better than their counterparts back home in 2001, while men show no difference; in the most recent wave, both men and women show a disadvantage with respect to BolBol, equally across all parental years of education. This effect is related to the increase in the period in the access and finalization of primary education in Bolivia, which is not observed in Argentina.

As regards *attainment of secondary education*, in both years and for both genders there is a disadvantage of BolAR with respect to BolBol, which is stronger for men. For both genders, in 2001 the gap is larger among those with higher educated parents; we also see that this is the only situation in which they experience a disadvantage with respect to native Argentines too. For the most recent wave, these patterns disappear: the negative gap with respect to those in origin remains, but stays equal across all parental years of education, while the negative gap with respect to native Argentines disappears (and just remains the positive gap among those with low educated parents).

5 Summary and discussion

Through the analysis of large-scale census microdata, this study has shown evidence of how educational outcomes and patterns of educational reproduction among the children of Bolivian migrants in Argentina, compare to those of native Argentine children and those of non-migrants at origin. In so doing, it has helped to fill in two gaps in the literature. First, how the outcomes of migrants and their children compare to those who did not migrate; and second, how migrant integration patterns appear in the Global South. The article started by exploring how patterns of educational reproduction occur most generally among the general population, and in particular in the two countries studied: Argentina and Bolivia. It then moved on to elucidate what difference does it make to have migrant origins and what the impact of moving across contexts with different patterns of educational reproduction may be.

As regards the comparison of Bolivian-origin individuals in Argentina with native Argentines, a first key finding—which has been observed for other migrant-origin groups in countries in the Global North (Crul et al., 2017; Kim & Kulkarni, 2009; Oberdabernig & Schneebaum, 2017)—is

that Bolivian-origin children tend to be more educationally mobile than native Argentines. This lower mobility, implies, for the case under study, that these children have better educational attainments than native Argentines among those who have low educated parents, who also constitute the majority. As discussed initially, while Goldthorpe's arguments on the mechanisms of educational reproduction may work when talking about the native population of a country, they may not necessarily apply to migrants and their children. Evidence of motivation and parental encouragement, found in qualitative studies in Argentina, may be a plausible explanation for this finding, which has also been observed for other migrant-origin groups in Argentina (Author, XX).

A second key finding is that among those who have better educated parents, migrant origin children are doing worse than native Argentines, but only in 2001 and for secondary attainment. I argued that this negative effect might be related with a lack of compensatory resources—which I was not able to fully capture with the available data. While the more universalistic access to primary education might explain why we do not see a penalty for completing this level, it is an open question why the effect for secondary completion changes from negative to null between both waves⁶. A hint might be found in Figure 3, which shows that Argentine's probabilities of high school completion reduce for those with better educated parents between both waves (at least for those who cohabit with their parents), though it remains uncertain why this happens. Another factor might be related to a strengthening of the migrant network—another element that emerged in qualitative research—and its ability to compensate for a lack of compensatory resources. What remains clear is that patterns of educational reproduction of Bolivian-origin individuals in Argentina seem to be less susceptible to the change of period, compared to those observed for natives in both origin and destination countries (even if the two periods most likely refer to two different migrant waves). More research is certainly needed to disentangle these effects.

As regards the comparison with Bolivia, the picture is quite different. A fourth key finding of this analysis is that even under the assumption that migrants are presumably positively selected in terms of unobserved characteristics—such as their motivation to improve their lives and that of their children—, my results suggest that migration to Argentina did not bring benefits to the educational outcomes of their children, at least in terms of the indicators analysed. The greater educational expansion experienced by Bolivia—which benefited principally children from low-educated families—coupled with the fact that those who left for Argentina were, in general, from such less advantaged families, means that they may have missed those (potential) gains their counterparts got back home.

A fifth key finding is that, similar to the comparison with native Argentineans, we see in the first wave that when compared to those who remained, the children of high educated migrant parents—even if a minority—experience the highest losses in terms of secondary attainment (men especially). Again, this would go in line with the arguments about lack of compensatory resources and the greater inability of migrant parents to transmit that capital to their children. In the next wave, however, both Bolivia and Argentina experience a reduction in the educational reproduction at the top, coupled, in Bolivia only, with a greater mobility from the bottom. This leads to see a change in the gaps between Bolivian-origin individuals in Argentina and Bolivians in Bolivia, which now become similar across parental educational levels (as said before, Bolivia has greater top reproduction than Argentina: the gap with respect to native Bolivians therefore remains in the second wave, while that with respect to native Argentineans disappears).

⁶ In a previous paper (Author XX), based on the full Argentine census data, I do find a negative effect for pooled men and women from 19 to 21 years old. This effect is, however, small compared to the ones observed for other South American-origin groups—for whom I find a similar pattern, especially those with Paraguayan origins—and is restrained only to those with the highest educated parents (16-19 years of education), who are minority among Bolivians.

Finally, it is interesting to observe what happens with differences between men and women. Migrant-origin men seem to be the most negatively affected with respect to men in Bolivia, while for women differences are smaller. Looking more closely, we see that the slight advantage that women in Bolivia have over men (among co-residents only) is observed for the children of migrants too, but much bigger. This suggests that migration to Argentina may actually increase the differences between men and women, in a way adapting to the Argentinean case, where Argentinean women greatly surpass Argentinean men.

Overall, the results suggest that Bolivian-origin individuals born in Argentina and co-residing with their parents—most of them low educated—occupy an intermediate position: they tend to do better than natives in destination, but worse than those who remained (with migrant-origin men being the most negatively affected). The next question is: does this mean that Bolivians (and their children) have “lost” when they moved to Argentina? In terms of attainment perhaps: next to being an asset in itself, a better education is an extra tool that allows acquiring other types of assets, such as a better job, or a higher income. While of course this will vary by country, having a secondary degree is always better than not having it. In the case of Argentina and Bolivia, for example, greater education leads to an increase in the occupational status to a similar extent (as observed in 2001 data). Having said that, educational attainment—a commonly used indicator in studies of social stratification and mobility—is just one measure of many possible ones, and it remains an open question how much it can truly reveal in terms of gains and losses. The reason I pose this question, and which I expect to explore in future work, is that the results of national tests applied to schoolchildren only partially confirm my findings. On the one hand, previous studies done with Argentinean national tests (APRENDER) find, in line with my findings, that Bolivian-origin individuals in Argentina do indeed better than native Argentines, once socioeconomic background has been considered (Cerrutti & Binstock, 2019). On the other hand, however, national and regional (TERCE) tests applied in both countries suggest that Bolivia is doing worse than Argentina (Cayumán, Henríquez, Valenzuela, & Gatica, 2020; Flotts et al., 2015). This would suggest that Bolivian-origin children may have actually benefited from the move. While all these arguments represent a supposition, since in practice we cannot observe how these migrant-origin children would have performed in Bolivia, these counterintuitive results make me consider these results with caution and invite me, and the reader, to continue thinking about how to better understand the impact of migration. I hope, nevertheless, that the multiple comparisons presented here provide new insights to integration studies and the outcomes of migration in the Global South.

6 Bibliography

- Bakewell, O. (2009). *South-South migration and human development: reflections on African experiences*. Retrieved from Munich:
- Beauchemin, C. (2014). A manifesto for quantitative multi-sited approaches to international migration. *International Migration Review*, 48(4), 921-938. doi:10.1111/imre.12157
- Beech, J., & Princz, P. (2012). Migraciones y educación en la Ciudad de Buenos Aires: tensiones políticas, pedagógicas y étnicas. *Revista Latinoamericana de Educación Inclusiva*, 6, 53-71.
- Behtoui, A., & Neergaard, A. (2009). Perceptions of discrimination in recruitment and the workplace. *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies*, 7(4), 347 - 369. Retrieved from <http://www.informaworld.com/10.1080/15562940903378813>
- Bengochea, J., & Pellegrino, A. (2023). Etapas de la migración internacional e intrarregional en América Latina y el Caribe. *Notas de Población*, 116, 137-157.
- Bernardi, F. (2014). Compensatory advantage as a mechanism of educational inequality: a regression discontinuity based on month of birth. *Sociology of Education*, 87(2), 74-88. doi:10.1177/0038040714524258
- Blau, P., & Duncan, O. D. (1967). *The American occupational structure*. New York: Wiley.

- Borjas, G. J. (1995). Ethnicity, neighborhoods, and human-capital externalities. *The American Economic Review*, 85(3), 365-390. doi:10.3386/w4912
- Breen, R., & Müller, W. (Eds.). (2020). *Education and intergenerational social mobility in Europe and the United States*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Campillo-Carrete, B. (2013). *South-South migration: a review of the literature*. Retrieved from Canada (<http://hdl.handle.net/10625/52465>):
- Carrasco, I., & Suárez, J. I. (2019). Inmigración e inclusión laboral y protección social según el origen y el tiempo de residencia de los migrantes en países seleccionados de América Latina. *Notas de Población*, 108, 99-131.
- Cayumán, C., Henríquez, C., Valenzuela, P., & Gatica, F. (2020). *Aplicación del Tercer Estudio Regional Comparativo y Explicativo (TERCE). Diagnóstico nacional de Bolivia*. Retrieved from Santiago:
- Cebolla-Boado, H., González Ferrer, A., & Nuhoğlu Soysal, Y. (2021). It is all about “Hope”: evidence on the immigrant optimism paradox. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 44(2), 252-271. doi:10.1080/01419870.2020.1745254
- Cerrutti, M. (2009). *Diagnóstico de las poblaciones de inmigrantes en la Argentina*. Retrieved from Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires:
- Cerrutti, M., & Binstock, G. (2019). Migración, adolescencia y educación en Argentina: desentrañando las brechas de aprendizajes. *Revista Latinoamericana de Población*, 13(24).
- Cerrutti, M., & Parrado, E. (2015). Intraregional migration in South America: trends and a research agenda. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 41, 399-421. doi:10.1146/annurev-soc-073014-112249
- Chiswick, B. R., & DebBurman, N. (2004). Educational attainment: analysis by immigrant generation. *Economics of Education Review*, 23(4), 361-379. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6VB9-4B6KDXP-1/2/6726bf9bb8fe8cadcd8071413ca69104>
- Cruces, G., Domench, C. G., & Gasparini, L. (2012). *Inequality in education: evidence for Latin America*. Retrieved from La Plata:
- Crul, M., Schneider, J., Keskiner, E., & Lelie, F. (2017). The multiplier effect: how the accumulation of cultural and social capital explains steep upward social mobility of children of low-educated immigrants. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 40(2), 321-338. doi:10.1080/01419870.2017.1245431
- Dalle, P., Jorrat, J. R., & Riveiro, M. (2018). Movilidad social intergeneracional. In J. I. Piovani & A. n. Salvia (Eds.), *La Argentina en el siglo XXI: cómo somos, vivimos y convivimos en una sociedad desigual: encuesta nacional sobre la estructura social*. Ciudad de Buenos Aires: Siglo XXI Editores.
- Dawkins, C. J. (2004). Recent evidence on the continuing causes of black-white residential segregation. *Journal of Urban Affairs*, 26(3), 379-400. doi:10.1111/j.0735-2166.2004.00205.x
- Di Stasio, V., & Heath, A. (2019). *Are employers in Britain discriminating against ethnic minorities?* Retrieved from Oxford: <http://csi.nuff.ox.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Are-employers-in-Britain-discriminating-against-ethnic->
- Domenech, E. E. (2014). “Bolivianos” en la “Escuela Argentina”: Representaciones acerca de los hijos de inmigrantes bolivianos en una escuela de la periferia urbana. *REMHU - Rev. Interdiscipl. Mobil. Hum.*, 42, 171-188.
- Feliciano, C. (2005). Educational selectivity in U.S. immigration: how do immigrants compare to those left behind? *Demography*, 42(1), 131-152. doi:10.1353/dem.2005.0001
- Feliciano, C. (2020). Immigrant selectivity effects on health, labor market, and educational outcomes. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 46(1), 315-334. doi:10.1146/annurev-soc-121919-054639
- Feliciano, C., & Lanuza, Y. R. (2017). An immigrant paradox? Contextual attainment and intergenerational educational mobility. *American Sociological Review*, 82(1), 211-241. doi:doi:10.1177/0003122416684777

- Flotts, M. P., Manzi, J., Jiménez, D., Abarzúa, A., Cayuman, C., & García, M. J. (2015). *Informe de resultados TERCE. Tercer estudio regional comparativo y explicativo. Logros de aprendizaje. Laboratorio latinoamericano de evaluación de la calidad de la educación*. Retrieved from Santiago:
- Gavazzo, N., Beheran, M., & Novaro, G. (2014). La escolaridad como hito en las biografías de los hijos de bolivianos en Buenos Aires. *REMHU: Revista Interdisciplinaria da Mobilidade Humana*, 22(42).
- Gavazzo, N., & Espul, S. (2020). La educación de las nuevas generaciones como herramienta de ascenso social para las familias migrantes del Gran Buenos Aires. *Periplos, Revista de Investigación sobre Migraciones*, 4(1), 147-173.
- Goldthorpe, J. (2000). *On sociology. Numbers, narratives, and the integration of research and theory*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Guveli, A., Ganzeboom, H. B. G., Baykara-Krumme, H., Platt, L., Eroğlu, Ş., Spierings, N., . . . Sozeri, E. K. (2017). 2,000 Families: identifying the research potential of an origins-of-migration study. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 40(14), 2558-2576. doi:10.1080/01419870.2016.1234628
- Hanson, A., & Hawley, Z. (2011). Do landlords discriminate in the rental housing market? Evidence from an internet field experiment in US cities. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 70(2-3), 99-114. Retrieved from <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:eee:juecon:v:70:y:2011:i:2-3:p:99-114>
- Heath, A., & Cheung, S. Y. (Eds.). (2007). *Unequal chances. Ethnic minorities in Western labour markets*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Jiménez, M., & Jiménez, M. (2019). Intergenerational educational mobility in Latin America. An analysis from the equal opportunity approach. *Cuadernos de Economía*, 38(76), 289-330.
- Kao, G., & Thompson, J. (2003). Racial and ethnic stratification in educational achievement and attainment. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 29, 417-441. doi:10.1146/annurev.soc.29.010202.100019
- Kao, G., & Tienda, M. (1998). Educational aspirations of minority youth. *American Journal of Education*, 106(3), 349-384. doi:10.2307/1085583
- Kim, D. Y., & Kulkarni, V. S. (2009). The role of father's occupation on intergenerational educational and occupational mobility: the case of second-generation Chinese Americans in New York. *Sociological Forum*, 24(1), 104-134. doi:10.1111/j.1573-7861.2008.01088.x
- Lee, J., & Zhou, M. (2014). The success frame and achievement paradox: the costs and consequences for Asian Americans. *Race and Social Problems*, 6(1), 38-55. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12552-014-9112-7>
- Lemmi, S., Morzilli, M., & Moretto, O. (2018). “Para no trabajar de sol a sol”: Los sentidos de la educación en jóvenes y adultos/as integrantes de familias migrantes bolivianas hortícolas del Gran La Plata - Buenos Aires, Argentina. *RUNA, archivo para las ciencias del hombre*, 39(2), 117-136.
- Li, Y., & Heath, A. (2016). Class matters: a study of minority and majority social mobility in Britain, 1982–2011. *American Journal of Sociology*, 122(1), 162-200. doi:10.1086/686696
- Lieutier, A. (Ed.) (2019). *Condiciones de vida de migrantes en la República Argentina*: Organización Internacional para las Migraciones.
- Mera, G., & Marcos, M. (2015). Cartografías migratorias urbanas. Distribución espacial de la población extranjera en la Ciudad de Buenos Aires (2010). *Geograficando*, 11(1).
- Minnesota Population Center. (2020). *Integrated Public Use Microdata Series: International. Version 7.3 [dataset]*
- Muñoz, E. (2022). *The geography of intergenerational mobility in Latin America and the Caribbean*. Retrieved from Washington DC:
- Neidhöfer, G., Ciaschi, M., & Gasparini, L. (2021). *Intergenerational mobility in education in Latin America*. Retrieved from Caracas:

- Novaro, G. (2012). Niños inmigrantes en Argentina. Nacionalismo escolar, derechos educativos y experiencias de alteridad. *Revista Mexicana de Investigación Educativa*, 17(53), 459-483.
- Oberdabernig, D., & Schneebaum, A. (2017). Catching up? The educational mobility of migrants' and natives' children in Europe. *Applied Economics*, 49(37), 3701-3728. doi:10.1080/00036846.2016.1267843
- Oszlak, O. (1997). *La formación del estado argentino*. Buenos Aires: Editorial Planeta.
- Polavieja, J. G., Fernández-Reino, M., & Ramos, M. (2018). Are migrants selected on motivational orientations? Selectivity patterns amongst international migrants in Europe. *European Sociological Review*, 34(5), 570-588. doi:10.1093/esr/jcy025
- Portes, A., & Fernandez-Kelly, P. (2008). No margin for error: educational and occupational achievement among disadvantaged children of immigrants. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 620(1), 12-36. doi:10.1177/0002716208322577
- Sassone, S. M., & Cortes, G. (2014). Escalas del espacio migratorio de los bolivianos en la Argentina: entre la dispersión y la concentración. *Las migraciones bolivianas en la encrucijada interdisciplinar: evolución, cambios y tendencias*, 75-110. Retrieved from https://ddd.uab.cat/pub/caplli/2014/129435/migbolencint_a2014p75.pdf
- Sjaastad, L. A. (1962). The costs and returns of human migration. *Journal of Political Economy*, 70(5), 80-93. doi:<http://www.jstor.org/stable/1829105>
- Torche, F. (2021). *Intergenerational mobility in Latin America in comparative perspective*. . Retrieved from New York:
- UNDP. (2021). Regional Human Development Report 2021: Latin America and the Caribbean Region. *UNDP (United Nations Development Programme)*. Retrieved from https://www.latinamerica.undp.org/content/rblac/en/home/library/human_development/regional-human-development-report-2021.html
- United Nations; Department of Economic and Social Affairs; Population Division. (2017a). *Population Facts 2017/5*. Retrieved from
- United Nations; Department of Economic and Social Affairs; Population Division. (2017b). *Trends in International Migrant Stock: Migrants by Destination and Origin (United Nations database, POP/DB/MIG/Stock/Rev.2017)*.

Table A1: Distribution of control variables by group

	Bolivians in Bolivia (BolBol)	Bolivian-origin individuals in Argentina (BolAR)	Native argentineans (ArgArg)
single workless	11.63	10.60	9.92
single working	24.46	15.09	12.91
couple workless-workless	4.79	12.83	10.87
couple working-workless	29.07	36.12	38.54
couple working-working	30.05	25.36	27.76
owner	70.95	68.20	75.54
water	76.13	85.95	87.27
sewage	42.15	55.14	69.34
secuplus2045_dep	40.77	45.66	44.75
personsroom	2.86	2.35	1.88
age	12.74	13.30	14.51

Source: Own calculations based on IPUMS (2001, 2010 & 2012)

Table A2: Logistic regression models with all variables. B-coefficients and standard errors

	Men		Women	
	Primary+ (14-18)	Secondary+ (19-25)	Primary+ (14-18)	Secondary+ (19-25)
BolAR	0.135 (0.157)	-0.975 (0.144)***	0.634 (0.168)***	-0.119 (0.138)
ArgArg	-1.111 (0.034)***	-2.083 (0.032)***	-0.188 (0.036)***	-1.271 (0.035)***
2010/2012	1.099 (0.053)***	0.500 (0.038)***	1.451 (0.056)***	0.622 (0.042)***
BolAR*2010/2012	-1.201 (0.242)***	-0.282 (0.204)	-1.555 (0.245)***	-0.556 (0.205)**
ArgArg*2010/2012	-1.348 (0.061)***	-0.504 (0.047)***	-1.520 (0.066)***	-0.590 (0.050)***
YearEduParents	0.141 (0.005)***	0.156 (0.004)***	0.179 (0.005)***	0.185 (0.004)***
BolAR* YearEduParents	-0.056 (0.028)*	-0.055 (0.020)**	-0.063 (0.029)*	-0.102 (0.022)***
ArgArg*YearEduParents	0.056 (0.006)***	0.065 (0.004)***	0.016 (0.006)*	0.029 (0.005)***
2010/2012*YearEduParents	-0.043 (0.008)***	-0.078 (0.005)***	-0.066 (0.009)***	-0.105 (0.006)***
BolAR*2010/2012* YearEduParents	0.007 (0.038)	0.074 (0.027)**	0.001 (0.038)	0.109 (0.030)***
ArgArg*2010/2012* YearEduParents	-0.001 (0.009)	0.050 (0.005)***	-0.004 (0.010)	0.067 (0.006)***
age	0.293 (0.004)***	0.141 (0.002)***	0.312 (0.005)***	0.137 (0.002)***
psecuplus2045_dep	0.015 (0.001)***	0.014 (0.000)***	0.015 (0.001)***	0.014 (0.000)***
single working	0.122	-0.031	0.084	-0.015

	Men		Women	
	Primary+ (14-18)	Secondary+ (19-25)	Primary+ (14-18)	Secondary+ (19-25)
couple workless-workless	0.040 (0.023)***	0.063 (0.018)	-0.063 (0.026)**	0.078 (0.019)
couple working-workless	0.192 (0.026)	0.160 (0.020)**	0.125 (0.030)*	0.199 (0.022)***
couple working-working	0.271 (0.021)***	0.207 (0.016)***	0.155 (0.024)***	0.219 (0.017)***
overcrowd	-0.194 (0.023)***	-0.350 (0.017)***	-0.166 (0.026)***	-0.389 (0.018)***
owner	0.023 (0.004)***	0.212 (0.006)***	0.045 (0.004)***	0.163 (0.006)***
sewageyes	0.392 (0.014)	0.477 (0.012)***	0.399 (0.016)**	0.507 (0.013)***
pipewat	0.130 (0.013)***	0.254 (0.011)***	0.214 (0.015)***	0.295 (0.012)***
_cons	-3.707 (0.017)***	-4.098 (0.015)***	-4.506 (0.019)***	-3.865 (0.016)***
<i>N</i>	332,835 (0.077)***	307,359 (0.060)***	314,224 (0.089)***	262,555 (0.067)***

* p-value<0.5 ** p-value<0.1 *** p-value<0.01

Source: Own calculations based on IPUMS (2001, 2010 & 2012)